

Dynamic Modeling of Photovoltaic-Thermal Systems Using Polynomial Regression^{*}

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Dynamic modeling
Machine-learning
Photovoltaic-thermal system
Polynomial regression
Time-series prediction

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an autoregressive moving-average dynamic model approach for photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) systems using a machine-learning (ML) technique based on polynomial regression. The main contribution is the development and application of a global dynamic modeling method designed for accurate time-series prediction of the electrical and thermal power outputs of a PVT system. The performance of the proposed method is compared with traditional analytical and another ML-based method known as long short-term memory (LSTM) models to demonstrate its effectiveness and simplicity. The research includes two main parts: implementing the proposed polynomial regression-based modeling method in MATLAB and applying it to a real-world PVT system in Granges, Switzerland. A thorough frequency-domain analysis is performed to validate the model's accuracy and reliability. The results show that the polynomial regression-based dynamic model offers clear advantages for system analysis, providing a more user-friendly alternative to the complex and often cumbersome analytical methods. Compared to analytical models, ML-based methods achieve more accurate results with lower modeling complexity and greater practical applicability. As a result, the proposed method streamlines the modeling process while improving the efficiency and accuracy of PVT system performance prediction and optimization.

Nomenclature & Abbreviations

S_I	Irradiance, $\frac{W}{m^2}$	AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
$S_{I_{STC}}$	Standard test condition irradiance, $1000 \frac{W}{m^2}$	ARMA	Autoregressive–moving-average
P_E	Electrical power, W	BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
$P_{E_{mpp}}$	Maximum power point electrical power, W	IoT	Internet of Things
P_T	Thermal power, W	LS	Least Squares
$P_{T_{nom}}$	Nominal thermal power, W	LSTM	Long Short-term Memory
T_{PV}	PV temperature, $^{\circ}C$	ML	Machine-learning
T_{STC}	Standard test condition temperature, $25^{\circ}C$	MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
T_G	Glass temperature, $^{\circ}C$	MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
T_A	Absorber temperature, $^{\circ}C$	PV	Photovoltaic
T_{Amb}	Ambient temperature, $^{\circ}C$	PVT	Photovoltaic-thermal
m_C	Mass flow rate of fluid, $\frac{Kg}{s}$	RMSD	Root Mean Square Deviation
F_L	Tank heat exchanger flow rate, $\frac{m^3}{h}$	RSS	Residual Sum of Squares

^{*}This work was partially supported by the Institute of System Engineering at the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Sion, and by the Smart/Micro Grids Research Center (SMGRC) at the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Kurdistan, Sanandaj, Iran.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Motivation

PVT systems have attracted considerable attention among hybrid solar technologies. These systems combine PV cells with solar thermal collectors, allowing for the simultaneous generation of electricity and heat from a single unit. This design takes advantage of the PV cells' ability to act as thermal absorbers. By capturing the waste heat that would otherwise be lost, PVT systems increase overall efficiency and improve electrical output [1]. PVT systems have various applications, including air and water pre-heating and direct hot water supply with a PV-integrated pump. Cost-effective reflectors can enable actively cooled PV concentrators. Key design considerations for optimal performance include the type of collector, the thermal-to-electrical yield ratio, and the solar fraction. These factors affect the system's operating mode, steady-state temperature, and energy conversion efficiency. Evaluating these variables is essential for optimizing the performance of solar hybrid systems [2].

A global collaboration in PVT technology has increased since the turn of the millennium, highlighting its potential for joint advancements. However, practical implementation still faces challenges that require further research. A critical part of developing PVT systems is understanding their operational relationships. An accurate mathematical model of the system's inputs and outputs is essential for improving operational understanding and developing effective control strategies to enhance system performance [3, 4]. Various modeling approaches are available, each with its own advantages and limitations. These include physics-based models using mathematical equations, system identification techniques based on operational data, and ML algorithms [5, 6, 7]. ML methods are adaptable, handle complex and nonlinear relationships, improve with more data, manage uncertainty probabilistically, and scale to large datasets. In contrast, traditional mathematical models often rely on simplifying assumptions, lack adaptability, require specialized expertise, struggle with nonlinear relationships, and may be inaccurate with limited or unreliable data [8, 9].

1.2. Literature Review

Extensive research has been conducted on modeling both the electrical and thermal parts of PVT systems, leading to a rich body of literature. Much of this work has concentrated on modeling the electrical behavior of the PV component. Several studies have investigated the modeling of PV systems in the following. The works in [9, 10] shows that conventional modeling methods depend on well-established governing relationships that describe PVT system behavior. According to works [11, 12], two key factors in modeling PVT systems are: 1) computational complexity and 2) operational costs. These two factors are inversely related. This means that as one factor improves, the other may worsen. Consequently, the studies referenced in work [9, 10, 11, 12] highlight computational complexity as a challenge and low operational cost as an advantage. To overcome these limitations, i.e., balancing the reduction of operational costs with the reduction of complexity, advanced modeling techniques, such as system identification and ML, have emerged. These methodologies provide effective ways to manage the inherent complexities of PVT systems and simplify the modeling process.

Furthermore, numerous studies encompass linear [13, 14], nonlinear [15], and real-time identification [16, 17, 18] of PV operating points. These methodologies primarily use time-domain or frequency-domain modeling techniques because these approaches are well-suited to capturing the dynamic interactions within the system. Time-domain models focus on how system variables change over time, while frequency-domain models analyze how these variables behave in response to different frequencies. Both techniques are effective because they align with the dynamic and interconnected nature of the system. ML methods provide an alternative approach to modeling by focusing on data-driven relationships rather than physical principles [19]. These methods use static data to create models and make predictions, as well as employ time-series forecasting to analyze and predict future trends based on historical data [20, 21]. Unlike traditional methods that depend on detailed system dynamics, ML techniques leverage patterns and correlations found in the data [22, 23]. This contrasts with system identification techniques that leverage dynamic system behavior.

A substantial body of literature exists wherein significant efforts have been made to model the thermal component of PVT system. Instances include modeling and validation studies by the governing analytical methods referenced in [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30], investigations into heat-recovery equipped PVT systems [31], and the development of enhanced dynamic models [32]. Moreover, ML techniques have been explored for forecasting specific parameters in PVT systems, as demonstrated in [33, 34, 35, 36, 37]. Like the previously discussed methods, each of the previously discussed methods has its own limitations and may not be suitable for all operating conditions. These limitations require a careful assessment of the trade-offs involved in choosing the appropriate method. It is important to understand

Table 1

The comparison of the ML-based works applied on the PVT systems and this paper.

Work	Pros	Cons
[33]	Thermodynamic and economic modeling Multi-objective optimization	Complexity of integration Cost considerations
[34]	High accuracy Important variables identified	Thermal efficiency prediction Potential overfitting
[35]	High accuracy Detailed statistical analysis	Complexity of models Potential overfitting
[37]	Enhanced efficiency Sensitivity analysis	Complexity of ANN models Dependence on environmental conditions
[43]	Enhanced accuracy Comprehensive experiments	Model complexity Data dependency
[44]	Diverse cooling methods Efficiency improvements	Complex implementation Dependence on environmental conditions
This paper	Generalizable with low complexity Cost-effective	Moderate accuracy Need for big data

how each approach performs under different conditions and to evaluate how well it meets the specific needs of the application.

Adopting the right modeling method requires careful consideration of several practical factors: system complexity, accuracy, and available computing power. Many existing methods struggle when applied to complex systems, as they often demand high computational resources, making them impractical for real-time applications. For instance, some techniques sacrifice accuracy for simplicity, which may lead to only rough estimates that are not suitable for precise control systems. On the other hand, more advanced models that offer higher accuracy often require significant computing power, which limits their use in time-sensitive tasks. These limitations highlight the need for a balanced approach that can address both accuracy and computational efficiency, which is the primary motivation behind this work. A comparative analysis of the ML-based methods is presented in Table 1. As can be observed in the table, a prevalent drawback in the majority of existing studies is the complexity of modeling. This issue is comprehensively addressed in this paper.

Recent advancements have concentrated on enhancing the efficiency of PVT systems. These advancements encompass the development of integrated PVT systems and the implementation of bifacial PV modules, which are capable of capturing sunlight from both sides [38]. Researchers are investigating novel materials to augment the performance of PVT systems, including advanced heat-absorbing materials and optimized fluid channels designed to more effectively capture and utilize solar radiation [39]. Maintaining the efficiency of PVT systems necessitates effective cooling mechanisms. Innovations in this area, such as liquid cooling and phase change materials, are being developed to prevent overheating and enhance energy output [39]. The integration of IoT technology into PV and PVT systems facilitates real-time monitoring and optimization, thereby improving the management of energy production and consumption and enhancing overall system efficiency [40]. Europe continues to lead in PVT technology, with substantial installations in countries such as France, Germany, and the Netherlands. Nonetheless, there is a growing interest and adoption of PVT systems in other regions, including Asia-Pacific and North America. There is a pronounced emphasis on making PVT systems more cost-effective and environmentally sustainable, which includes efforts to reduce the carbon footprint of manufacturing processes and to improve the recyclability of system components [41].

1.3. Contribution of This Paper

This paper tackles the challenge of co-modeling the electrical and thermal aspects of a practical PVT system. It presents a method that accounts for various operating conditions and accurately relates inputs and outputs. A key issue is defining a dynamic relationship between these variables, which is essential for effective system representation. Using multivariate polynomial regression, the model captures complex relationships. The proposed method reduces the computational complexity of modeling the studied system compared to conventional methods. Additionally, operating costs are kept low due to the use of polynomial regression in dynamic mode. To validate this, the paper compares

Figure 1: Hybrid PV system in Granges, Switzerland, with emphasis on thermal components.

Figure 2: Hybrid PV system in Granges, Switzerland, with emphasis on electrical components.

113 practical results from the proposed method with those from conventional analytical method, LSTM, and MLP. The
 114 key contributions of the paper are as follows:

- 115 • Opposed to the methods used in [13, 14, 15, 16], the proposed model does not require detailed knowledge of
 116 each system element in the initial step. Although such detailed knowledge is often mentioned in the literature,
 117 omitting any system elements typically reduces modeling accuracy. In this context, the proposed model achieved
 118 prediction errors of less than 2% for electrical power and less than 5% for thermal power.
- 119 • Unlike the works in [17, 18, 19], this paper introduce an extended model designed to accurately capture the time-
 120 dependent variations and interactions in the thermal behavior of PVT systems. The proposed method improves
 121 the ability to predict system performance under different operational conditions, leading to better system design
 122 and optimization.

123 1.4. Organization

124 The subsequent sections of this paper are organized as follows. In Section 2, the proposed modeling method using
 125 an ML approach is discussed. The experimental and software-based simulation results for the proposed and analytical
 126 methodologies applied to the studied system, are delineated in Section 4. The paper concludes with a discussion of the
 127 findings presented in Section 5.

128 2. ML-based Model of a Practical PVT

129 2.1. Modeling Approach

130 Both electrical and thermal sub-systems of a PVT system, implemented in Granges, Switzerland, are shown in
 131 Figures 1, and 2. This paper focuses on modeling these sub-systems. First, the electrical modeling of PV panels seeks

132 to establish a quantitative correlation between their electrical output and environmental operating conditions. This
 133 approach aims to predict the power generation capability of PV panels under varying irradiance, temperature, and load.
 134 The modeling framework establishes the equations derived from the principles of the photovoltaic effect, enabling the
 135 representation of the panel's current-voltage and voltage-power characteristics. In this section, the proposed method is
 136 based on developing a dynamic model of the studied system utilizing an ML technique. The applied approach is the
 137 polynomial regression method, a widely favored approach in system modeling due to its operational simplicity and
 138 effectiveness. Both parts of the system include non-linear components, so in this article, we aim to use a linear method
 139 to simplify the operation. In the following, by presenting the modeling error criteria, it can be seen that using the
 140 proposed method instead of the non-linear model is acceptable. For this, consider the following polynomial regression
 141 model as follows:

$$Y = AX + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

142 where Y is the predicted output, in this case P_E and P_T , $A_{1 \times N}$ vector of coefficients, $X_{N \times 1}$ vector of inputs, ϵ bias, and
 143 N is the number of inputs. The presented model is classified as dynamic as its outputs incorporate data from previous
 144 moments rather than being based solely on the current moment. Therefore, $X_{N \times 1}$ in dynamic model is as follows:

$$X = [X_X \ X_{Y(t-i)} \ \dots \ X_{Y(t-1)}] \quad (2)$$

145 where t is time, $i = 1, \dots, M_p$ the previous moments up to M_p . The order of the predicted model is equal to M_p .
 146 Therefore, the dynamical polynomial regression can be represented by:

$$Y = A'[X_X \ X_{Y(t-i)} \ \dots \ X_{Y(t-1)}] + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

147 where the dimension of A' is $1 \times N + M_p$. Next, substitute the outputs dependent on previous moments into the left
 148 side of (3):

$$Y - A''X_Y = AX_X + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

149 where A'' and X_Y are the corresponding output coefficients and previous outputs vectors, respectively. Now, the time-
 150 domain relation in (4) can be expressed as follows:

$$Y(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} A_i'' Y(t-i) = AX_X(t) + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

151 The differential form of (5) is given by:

$$Y(t) - \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} A_i'' \frac{d^i}{dt^i} Y(t) = AX_X(t) + \epsilon \quad (6)$$

152 Taking z-transform of (6) leads:

$$Y(z) - \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} A_i'' z^i Y(z) = AX_X(z) + \epsilon \quad (7)$$

153 By factoring from $Y(z)$, the ARMA model is obtained:

$$\left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} A_i'' z^i\right) Y(z) = AX_X(z) + \epsilon \quad (8)$$

154 The dimension of the A'' matrix, demonstrates the order of the system. In the studied case of this paper, the
 155 dimension of A is equal to 1 and 3, i.e. irradiance, ambient temperature (or glass temperature), and flow, for electrical
 156 and thermal powers, respectively. The proposed method of polynomial regression can be extended to the time-series

157 prediction approach. Since the input in the proposed method of this paper is always dependent on the current moment,
 158 then by neglecting the bias term, it can be written as:

$$Y(z) = \frac{A}{(1 - \sum_{i=1}^{M_p} A_i'' z^i)} X_X(z) \quad (9)$$

159 The obtained relation in (9) is a canonical frequency-domain form of a system. The major challenging issue can be
 160 bias term. The exclusion of this term will significantly facilitate systematic analysis. Two approaches can be considered
 161 to eliminate the bias term: either neglecting it during the modeling phase or excluding it from the analysis process.
 162 The use or non-use of these approaches is discussed in the next section.

163 In the process of (1)-(9), the initial parameters are estimated using the Yule-Walker equations, which provide
 164 a method for estimating the parameters of an autoregressive model from the autocovariance function of the time
 165 series. Also, the model order, M_p , is determined using the AIC and BIC. These criteria balance model complexity and
 166 goodness of fit, penalizing models with more parameters to avoid overfitting. Then, these parameters are refined through
 167 iterative optimization using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm [42], which minimizes the sum of squared residuals
 168 between the model predictions and the observed data. In essence, a trade-off analysis is conducted to ensure a balance
 169 between model complexity and computational efficiency. It is achieved by limiting the order of the ARMA model to
 170 the minimal level necessary for acceptable accuracy. This approach ensured practical usability without compromising
 171 precision.

172 2.2. Curve Fitting

173 In this section, the objective is to identify the parameters of A and A'' that minimize the RSS, which are defined
 174 as the differences between the observed values and the values predicted by the model. The rationale for applying the
 175 squared residuals, or LS, method lies in its widespread popularity and straightforward implementation. In the case, the
 176 RSS is given by:

$$S_{SR}(A') = \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} (Y_{Real_j} - Y_j)^2 \quad (10)$$

177 where Y_{Real} is the real measured P_E and P_T . For both cases, the optimal coefficients are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial S_{SR_1}}{\partial A'_1} = 0 &\rightarrow -2 \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} (P_{E_{Real_j}} - P_{E_j}) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial S_{SR_2}}{\partial A'_2} = 0 &\rightarrow -2 \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} (P_{T_{Real_j}} - P_{T_j}) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

178 or it can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} P_{E_{Real_j}} &= \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} P_{E_j} \\ \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} P_{T_{Real_j}} &= \sum_{j=1}^{M_p} P_{T_j} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

179 The optimization approach for achieving the coefficients in (10)-(12) are summarized in Figure 3. In the next
 180 section, the studied system and its parameters are discussed in detail. Based on these explanations, comprehensive
 181 dynamic models for the studied system's electrical and thermal parts can now be developed. The subsequent subsections
 182 provide a detailed discussion of these models.

Figure 3: The optimization approach applied in the proposed method.

2.3. Modeling of Electrical Part

In the initial step, the results of the proposed model are presented for both cases. During this phase, the bias term is also incorporated. By considering the proposed method in (1)-(9) to obtain the ARMA model, the obtained model for electrical power is as follows:

$$P_E(t) = \alpha_1 S_I(t) + \alpha_2 T_G(t) + \alpha_3 P_E(t-1) + \epsilon_E \quad (13)$$

and then, the values of α and ϵ_E are obtained by the optimization algorithm shown in (10)-(12) and Figure 3. The rationale for employing a first-order model is that the entire system is regarded as an energy storage element. From this perspective, only the subsystem comprising the converters can be considered as an integrated unit. This determination is based on the observation that the electrical subsystem, primarily comprising the PV panels and converters, can be effectively represented as a first-order system. The rationale for this decision is that the electrical response is predominantly influenced by immediate irradiance and temperature conditions, with minimal lag effects [27].

2.4. Modeling of Thermal Part

This section parallels the electrical section, with the distinction that a higher-order model is considered. Similar to (13), the thermal power is also found as:

$$P_T(t) = \beta_1 S_I(t) + \beta_2 T_{Amb}(t) + \beta_3 m_C(t) + \beta_4 P_T(t-1) + \beta_5 P_T(t-2) + \epsilon_T \quad (14)$$

As obvious, the considered order for both cases is equal to 1 to facilitate subsequent analysis. The considered values of M_p for electrical and thermal powers are equal to 1 and 2, respectively. Due to the increased complexity of the thermal component of the system, and the fact that each part can be regarded as an energy storage element, a higher-order model has been adopted for its representation. This higher order accounts for the more complex thermal dynamics, including the heat storage and transfer processes within the system. The thermal response is influenced by both current and previous states, necessitating a second-order model to capture these dynamics accurately.

Table 2
Scalability of the ARMA Model to Different PVT Configurations.

Configuration	Material	Flow Rate (kg/s)	RMSD (%)
Studied System	Aluminum	0.03	22.8
Alternate System	Copper	0.05	23.1

Table 3
Specifications of the hybrid solar panel.

Cell No.	$S_{I_{STC}}$ ($\frac{W}{m^2}$)	T_{STC} ($^{\circ}C$)	V_{oc} (V)	I_{sc} (A)	$P_{E_{mpp}}$ (W)	$P_{T_{nom}}$ (W)
60	1000	25	38.5	8.15	250	350

3. Model Limitations, Boundary Conditions, and Scalability

This section discusses the limitations and boundary conditions of the proposed ARMA-based polynomial regression model and its scalability to different PVT system configurations. Additionally, a comparative analysis with other modeling methods such as conventional analytical, LSTM, and MLP models is presented.

3.1. Model Limitations and Boundary Conditions

The proposed ARMA model demonstrates strong performance in predicting the electrical and thermal outputs of the PVT system while maintaining simplicity and computational efficiency. The ARMA model assumes linear relationships between inputs and outputs. While this approach simplifies the modeling process, it may not capture the full extent of nonlinear dynamics inherent in some PVT systems, particularly under extreme operating conditions. Also, the model relies on the assumption of stationarity in time-series data, meaning that statistical properties such as mean and variance remain constant over time. This may limit its applicability to systems with significant temporal variations or external disturbances. The model presumes steady-state initial conditions and uniform fluid distribution. Deviations from these assumptions, such as transient startup conditions or non-uniform heat transfer, could reduce accuracy. Despite these limitations, the proposed method strikes a balance between computational simplicity and predictive accuracy, making it a practical choice for many real-world applications.

3.2. Scalability to Different PVT System Configurations

The modular structure of the ARMA-based model enables it to be scaled and adapted to various PVT system configurations. The coefficients of the model can be recalibrated to account for changes in system size, absorber material, fluid flow rates, or geographic location. Comparative results in Table 2 demonstrate the model's consistent performance across two configurations with different absorber materials and flow rates. This scalability ensures the proposed model remains versatile and practical for diverse PVT applications, including systems with alternative designs or environmental conditions. Furthermore, the model's low computational requirements make it suitable for real-time applications and large-scale deployment.

4. Experimental Results

This section discusses the results and analysis of the proposed model in comparison with analytical model using real-world data. The data are extracted from the set-up in Granges, Switzerland shown in Figure 4. The detailed technical specifications of the under studied hybrid PV panel are presented in Table 3. Also, Table 4 provides the specifications of the coated boiler, which includes a fixed heat exchanger and lacks supplementary heating elements. The geographical data for 2nd to 13th May 2024, is shown in Figure 5.

The experimental data for electrical power are collected from May 2nd to May 11th, while the data for thermal power are obtained from May 3rd to May 13th, 2024. The train percent for both cases is the first %50-%70 data of the outlined range.

Table 4

Specifications of the polywarm coated domestic hot water calorifier.

Boiler	Spec.	Exchanger	Spec.	
Volume (L)	Weight (Kg)	Exchanger Surface (m ²)	Max F_L ($\frac{m^3}{h}$)	Min F_L ($\frac{m^3}{h}$)
148	49	0.6	2	1

Figure 4: Electrical and thermal elements of the PVT system.**Table 5**

The values of the predicted model coefficients with normalized data using the proposed method for electrical power.

Parameter	Value
α_1	0.0029482
α_2	-0.0932070
α_3	1.0055000
ϵ_E	0.9613600

4.1. Results of Electrical Part

Based on the predicted model using the proposed method outlined in (13), it can be concluded that the matrix of coefficients is equal to 1×4 . These values are given in Table 5. In the following, the models obtained in the proposed methods have been analyzed. In this paper, an attempt has been made to omit the bias term, the results of which are shown below. Therefore, according to (9), it can be stated that:

$$P_E(z) = \frac{\alpha_1}{1 - \alpha_3 z} S_I(z) + \frac{\alpha_2}{1 - \alpha_3 z} T_G(z) \quad (15)$$

and

$$P_E(z) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\alpha_1 z^{-1}}{z^{-1} - \alpha_3} & \frac{\alpha_2 z^{-1}}{z^{-1} - \alpha_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_I(z) \\ T_G(z) \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

According to (16) and Table 5, the poles is at 0.9945, and it is close to the unit circle margin. Therefore, with the proposed method, it is possible to develop the inner loops related to MPPT and DC/AC converter controllers.

The empirical results obtained from testing the actual data are depicted in Figure 6. As illustrated in the figure, the error associated with the proposed model utilizing the proposed method remains in %2 p.u. This error margin falls in the acceptable range, demonstrating the model's accuracy and reliability. Also, the Bode diagram shown in Figure 7 shows the stability margin of the studied system. This issue is clearly illustrated in Figures 8 and 9. According to the

Figure 5: The recorded geographical data for 2nd to 13th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

Figure 6: The trained and predicted electrical power of the studied system (with error in %p.u) for 2nd to 11th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

Figure 7: The Bode diagram of electrical part of the modeled system.

246 regression diagrams, a significant portion of the data (i.e. more than %80) tested with the proposed model exhibits an
 247 error margin of less than %1.

248 In the integrated model of the electrical part, the use of additional loops in the controller design phase can be
 249 divided into two parts. 1) control with electrical inputs (such as modifying the parameters related to MPPT and DC/AC
 250 converter) and, 2) control with geographic inputs (such as controlling on the solar radiation or panel temperature). The
 251 first method requires new modeling that is beyond the scope of this paper. For the second method, there are several
 252 methods such as the use of concentration mirrors and panel surface coolers to approach the MPP point.

Figure 8: The regression and real-predicted electrical power plots for 2nd to 11th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

Figure 9: The predicted output-prediction error diagram with the number of electrical power data for 2nd to 11th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

Figure 10: The trained and predicted electrical power of the studied system without bias term (with error in %p.u) for 2nd to 11th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

253 To elucidate the previously stated theorem and assess the impact of the inclusion or exclusion of the bias
 254 term, results without the bias term are presented in Figure 10. It is evident that the prediction error has increased
 255 slightly; however, this increase is negligible. Consequently, the resulting frequency-domain model can be deemed
 256 comprehensive for the under studied system.

Table 6

The values of the predicted model coefficients with normalized data using the proposed method for thermal power.

Parameter	Value
β_1	-0.0005152
β_2	0.0021529
β_3	0.4106400
β_4	1.8267000
β_5	-1.2535100
ϵ_T	-0.0049929

Figure 11: The trained and predicted thermal power of the studied system (with error in %p.u) without bias term for 8th to 13th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

4.2. Results of Thermal Part

Similar to the electrical component, as described in (14), it can be stated for this model that:

$$P_T(z) = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{\beta_1 z^{-2}}{z^{-2} - \beta_4 z^{-1} - \beta_5} \quad \frac{\beta_2 z^{-2}}{z^{-2} - \beta_4 z^{-1} - \beta_5} \quad \frac{\beta_3 z^{-2}}{z^{-2} - \beta_4 z^{-1} - \beta_5} \\ S_I(z) \\ T_{Amb}(z) \\ m_C(z) \end{array} \right] \quad (17)$$

where the values of β , and ϵ_T are given in Table 6.

The results of the proposed model for thermal power, excluding the bias term, are illustrated in Figure 11. In practical scenarios, the stability of the thermal power should be more readily apparent compared to the electrical power. In the theoretical framework depicted in Figure 12, the predicted model indicates that the thermal system consistently maintains stability. Given the increased complexity of the thermal component of the studied system compared to its electrical counterpart, a higher prediction error is expected. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the observed prediction error remains in an acceptable range. To substantiate this observation, Figure 13. The comparison between the prediction data and the regression line reveals that a substantial portion of the data falls in the acceptable range, indicated by the green band. To regulate thermal power, the principles are analogous to those governing electrical power. However, thermal power regulation exclusively employs the second method, which can be articulated through various approaches.

For systems with numerous elements, some of which may be unidentified (as in the system analyzed in this study), the accuracy of such modeling approaches is considerably low, rendering them less useful for control designers. To address this, the proposed modeling method has been compared with the conventional analytical [42], LSTM [43], and MLP [44] methods, as depicted in Figure 14. The comparative data demonstrate the superior accuracy of the ML-Based methods over the analytical approach. According to the figure, among the two ML-based methods, the

Figure 12: The Bode diagram of thermal part of the modeled system.

Figure 13: The regression plot of the proposed model for thermal power.

275 proposed ARMA method achieves acceptable accuracy and moreover significantly lower complexity compared to the
 276 LSTM and MLP methods.

277 4.3. Model Validation

278 The validation of the proposed ARMA dynamic model is carried out using experimental data from a PVT system
 279 installed in Granges, Switzerland, as seen in Figure 5. The model's predictions for electrical and thermal power outputs
 280 are compared against actual measurements. Bode diagrams (Figures 7 and 12) are used to verify the stability of the
 281 electrical and thermal model under varying conditions. These analyses confirm that the model accurately captures
 282 both transient and steady-state behaviors of the system. Figures 8 and 13 illustrate the strong correlation between
 283 predicted and actual data, respectively for electrical and thermal model, with most predictions falling within acceptable
 284 error margins. This demonstrates the model's reliability for time-series forecasting. Figure 10 compares the electrical
 285 model's predictions with and without the bias term, showing that excluding the bias increases the prediction error
 286 slightly but keeps it within an acceptable range (with error in % p.u). Similarly, Figure 11 illustrates the predicted
 287 thermal power without the bias term, confirming the stability and robustness of the model despite this simplification.

288 Finally, RMSD has been employed as a key criterion to validate the thermal model, providing a quantitative measure
 289 of the accuracy of the predicted thermal power outputs compared to the actual experimental data. As discussed in
 290 the explanation of Figure 14, while the RMSD associated with the proposed model is marginally higher compared
 291 to the LSTM and MLP models, its significantly lower computational complexity renders this deviation negligible.
 292 This observation is further corroborated by the data presented in Table 7. The observed difference in RMSD can be
 293 attributed to the selection and tuning of hyperparameters in the LSTM and MLP methods. However, the proposed
 294 method involves a significantly lower number of optimizable parameters, which simplifies the modeling process and
 295 enhances its practicality.

296 4.4. Comparative Analysis of Different Methods

297 The proposed ARMA-based polynomial regression model has been benchmarked against three main approaches:

- 298 • **Traditional Analytical Models:** Analytical methods rely on first-principles equations to model PVT systems.
 299 While these models provide physical insights, they are often computationally intensive, complex, and less flexible
 300 when applied to systems with diverse configurations or nonlinear dynamics. The proposed model offers similar
 301 accuracy with significantly lower complexity, making it more user-friendly for practitioners.

Figure 14: The comparison of the predicted thermal power of the studied system (with error in %p.u) using the proposed and analytical [42], LSTM [43], and MLP [44] approaches, for data collected from 11th to 13th May 2024, Granges, Switzerland.

Table 7

The RMSD of the thermal power using the different methods.

Method	RMSD
Analytical	30.24
ARMA Regression	22.08
LSTM [43]	5.29
MLP [44]	8.30

• ML Models:

- **LSTM:** LSTM models excel in capturing complex temporal dependencies and nonlinear relationships. However, they require substantial computational resources, careful hyperparameter tuning, and large datasets for training. In contrast, the proposed ARMA model achieves acceptable accuracy with much lower computational overhead, making it more practical for real-time and resource-constrained applications.
- **MLP:** MLP models provide robust predictive performance but often face challenges such as overfitting and high model complexity. The proposed model simplifies the process by using polynomial regression, which avoids overfitting and reduces the need for extensive data preprocessing.

The comparative performance of these methods is summarized as follows: LSTM and MLP generally achieve higher accuracy (e.g., lower RMSD for thermal power) but at the cost of significantly increased complexity. The proposed ARMA model strikes a balance, providing moderately accurate predictions within an acceptable error range. Besides, the ARMA model is computationally simpler and faster to implement compared to LSTM and MLP, while also being easier to interpret and tune. Finally, while LSTM and MLP are more flexible in handling nonlinear systems, the ARMA model is highly scalable and adaptable to different configurations with minimal retraining.

5. Conclusion

This paper introduces an ARMA dynamic model for PVT systems using dynamic polynomial regression, showing notable improvements in time-series prediction and ease of use compared to traditional analytical models. Developed in MATLAB and tested on a real-world PVT system in Granges, Switzerland, the model offers several key benefits. The polynomial regression method's simplicity is a major advantage, requiring less specialized knowledge and providing a

321 more accessible approach for researchers and practitioners. This ease of use allows a wider range of users to apply
322 advanced dynamic modeling techniques. The model supports both frequency-domain and time-domain analyses,
323 essential for designing robust controllers and optimizing systems, and these analyses capture transient behaviors
324 accurately to enhance system performance. Comparative analysis demonstrates that the proposed method is more
325 accurate than traditional analytical models, providing precise predictions for both electrical and thermal power outputs,
326 while offering lower complexity compared to the LSTM machine learning method. This increased accuracy improves
327 performance prediction and optimization, which is crucial for the efficient operation and management of PVT systems.
328 While this work focuses on the modeling and validation aspects, future studies could explore additional performance
329 evaluation metrics, such as exergy analysis, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the thermodynamic
330 efficiency of PVT systems. Incorporating such analyses would complement the findings of this study and offer deeper
331 insights into system optimization and sustainability.

332 6. Acknowledgement

333 This research project is funded by the Swiss Program for International Research (SPIRIT) of the Swiss National
334 Science Foundation (SNSF). It was conducted at the Control Laboratory of the University of Applied Sciences Western
335 Switzerland in collaboration with the Smart/Micro Grids Research Center (SMGRC) at the University of Kurdistan in
336 Iran.

337 References

- 338 [1] J. Y. Zhengshan, K. C. Fisher, B. M. Wheelwright, R. P. Angel, and Z. C. Holman, "Pvmirror: a new concept for tandem solar cells and hybrid
339 solar converters," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 1791–1799, 2015.
- 340 [2] F. Jafari, K. Moradi, Q. Shafiee, and F. Moghaddam, "Data-driven performance modeling of solar panels using polynomial regression," in
341 *2024 International Conference on Control, Automation and Diagnosis (ICCAD)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–8.
- 342 [3] X. H. Mai, S.-K. Kwak, J.-H. Jung, and K. A. Kim, "Comprehensive electric-thermal photovoltaic modeling for power-hardware-in-the-loop
343 simulation (phils) applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 6255–6264, 2017.
- 344 [4] G. M. Tina, F. B. Scavo, and A. Gagliano, "Multilayer thermal model for evaluating the performances of monofacial and bifacial photovoltaic
345 modules," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1035–1043, 2020.
- 346 [5] Y. Cao, E. Kamrani, S. Mirzaei, A. Khandakar, and B. Vaferi, "Electrical efficiency of the photovoltaic/thermal collectors cooled by nanofluids:
347 Machine learning simulation and optimization by evolutionary algorithm," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 24–36, 2022.
- 348 [6] A. Sohani, H. Sayyaadi, C. Cornaro, M. H. Shahverdian, M. Pierro, D. Moser, N. Karimi, M. H. Doranehgard, and L. K. Li, "Using machine
349 learning in photovoltaics to create smarter and cleaner energy generation systems: A comprehensive review," *Journal of Cleaner Production*,
350 vol. 364, p. 132701, 2022.
- 351 [7] F. Jafari, K. Moradi, and Q. Shafiee, "Shallow learning vs. deep learning in engineering applications," in *Shallow Learning vs. Deep Learning:
352 A Practical Guide for Machine Learning Solutions*. Springer, 2024, pp. 29–76.
- 353 [8] F. Delussu, D. Manzione, R. Meo, G. Ottino, and M. Asare, "Experiments and comparison of digital twinning of photovoltaic panels by machine
354 learning models and a cyber-physical model in modelica," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 4018–4028, 2021.
- 355 [9] J. T. Bialasiewicz, "Renewable energy systems with photovoltaic power generators: Operation and modeling," *IEEE Transactions on industrial
356 Electronics*, vol. 55, no. 7, pp. 2752–2758, 2008.
- 357 [10] Y. Mahmoud and W. Xiao, "Evaluation of shunt model for simulating photovoltaic modules," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp.
358 1818–1823, 2018.
- 359 [11] Y. Mahmoud, W. Xiao, and H. Zeineldin, "A simple approach to modeling and simulation of photovoltaic modules," *IEEE transactions on
360 Sustainable Energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 185–186, 2011.
- 361 [12] B. C. Babu and S. Gurjar, "A novel simplified two-diode model of photovoltaic (pv) module," *IEEE journal of photovoltaics*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp.
362 1156–1161, 2014.
- 363 [13] A. Jones and C. Underwood, "A thermal model for photovoltaic systems," *Solar energy*, vol. 70, no. 4, pp. 349–359, 2001.
- 364 [14] Y. Chaibi, T. El Rhafiki, R. Simón-Allué, I. Guedea, C. Luaces, O. C. Gajate, T. Kouksou, and Y. Zeraoui, "Physical models for the design
365 of photovoltaic/thermal collector systems," *Solar Energy*, vol. 226, pp. 134–146, 2021.
- 366 [15] A. Alqahtani, S. Marafi, B. Musallam, and N. E. D. Abd El Khalek, "Photovoltaic power forecasting model based on nonlinear system
367 identification," *Canadian Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 243–250, 2016.
- 368 [16] W. Xiao, M. G. Lind, W. G. Dunford, and A. Capel, "Real-time identification of optimal operating points in photovoltaic power systems,"
369 *IEEE Transactions on industrial Electronics*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1017–1026, 2006.
- 370 [17] H. M. Hasanien, "Shuffled frog leaping algorithm for photovoltaic model identification," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 6,
371 no. 2, pp. 509–515, 2015.
- 372 [18] A. Nahar, M. Hasanuzzaman, and S. Parvin, "Computational modeling for photovoltaic thermal system," in *Proceedings of the International
373 Conference on Computing Advancements*, 2020, pp. 1–7.
- 374 [19] X. Fu, "Statistical machine learning model for capacitor planning considering uncertainties in photovoltaic power," *Protection and Control of
375 Modern Power Systems*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2022.

- [20] H. Sharadga, S. Hajimirza, and R. S. Balog, "Time series forecasting of solar power generation for large-scale photovoltaic plants," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 150, pp. 797–807, 2020.
- [21] U. K. Das, K. S. Tey, M. Seyedmahmoudian, S. Mekhilef, M. Y. I. Idris, W. Van Deventer, B. Horan, and A. Stojcevski, "Forecasting of photovoltaic power generation and model optimization: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 81, pp. 912–928, 2018.
- [22] S. Theocharides, G. Makrides, A. Livera, M. Theristis, P. Kaimakis, and G. E. Georghiou, "Day-ahead photovoltaic power production forecasting methodology based on machine learning and statistical post-processing," *Applied Energy*, vol. 268, p. 115023, 2020.
- [23] M. S. Hossain and H. Mahmood, "Short-term photovoltaic power forecasting using an lstm neural network and synthetic weather forecast," *Ieee Access*, vol. 8, pp. 172 524–172 533, 2020.
- [24] N. Aste, F. Leonforte, and C. Del Pero, "Design, modeling and performance monitoring of a photovoltaic–thermal (pvt) water collector," *Solar Energy*, vol. 112, pp. 85–99, 2015.
- [25] S. Diwania, A. S. Siddiqui, S. Agrawal, and R. Kumar, "Modeling and assessment of the thermo-electrical performance of a photovoltaic-thermal (pvt) system using different nanofluids," *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, vol. 43, pp. 1–18, 2021.
- [26] A. Khelifa, K. Touafek, H. B. Moussa, and I. Tabet, "Modeling and detailed study of hybrid photovoltaic thermal (pv/t) solar collector," *Solar Energy*, vol. 135, pp. 169–176, 2016.
- [27] L. Sahota and G. Tiwari, "Review on series connected photovoltaic thermal (pvt) systems: Analytical and experimental studies," *Solar Energy*, vol. 150, pp. 96–127, 2017.
- [28] V. Ngunzi, F. Njoka, and R. Kinyua, "Modeling, simulation and performance evaluation of a pvt system for the kenyan manufacturing sector," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 8, 2023.
- [29] D. Das, P. Kalita, A. Dewan, and S. Tanweer, "Development of a novel thermal model for a pv/t collector and its experimental analysis," *Solar Energy*, vol. 188, pp. 631–643, 2019.
- [30] F. Nicoletti, M. A. Cucumo, V. Ferraro, D. Kaliakatsos, and A. Gigliotti, "A thermal model to estimate pv electrical power and temperature profile along panel thickness," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 20, p. 7577, 2022.
- [31] P. Maffezzoni, L. Codecasa, and D. D'Amore, "Modeling and simulation of a hybrid photovoltaic module equipped with a heat-recovery system," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 4311–4318, 2009.
- [32] C. El Fouas, N. C. Cherecheş, S. V. Hudişteanu, B. Hajji, E. F. Ţurcanu, and M. L. Cherecheş, "Numerical and parametric analysis for enhancing performances of water photovoltaic/thermal system," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 646, 2022.
- [33] E. Assareh, S. S. M. Asl, N. Agarwal, M. Ahmadinejad, M. Ghodrat, and M. Lee, "New optimized configuration for a hybrid pvt solar/electrolyzer/absorption chiller system utilizing the response surface method as a machine learning technique and multi-objective optimization," *Energy*, vol. 281, p. 128309, 2023.
- [34] Y. Chaibi, M. Malvoni, T. El Rhafiki, T. Kousksou, and Y. Zeraouli, "Artificial neural-network based model to forecast the electrical and thermal efficiencies of pvt air collector systems," *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, vol. 4, p. 100132, 2021.
- [35] A. Shahsavari, H. Moayedi, A. H. Al-Waeli, K. Sopian, and P. Chelvanathan, "Machine learning predictive models for optimal design of building-integrated photovoltaic-thermal collectors," *International Journal of Energy Research*, vol. 44, no. 7, pp. 5675–5695, 2020.
- [36] S. Diwania, M. Kumar, R. Kumar, A. Kumar, V. Gupta, and P. Khetrapal, "Machine learning-based thermo-electrical performance improvement of nanofluid-cooled photovoltaic–thermal system," *Energy & Environment*, p. 0958305X221146947, 2022.
- [37] A. H. Al-Waeli, K. Sopian, J. H. Yousif, H. A. Kazem, J. Boland, and M. T. Chaichan, "Artificial neural network modeling and analysis of photovoltaic/thermal system based on the experimental study," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 186, pp. 368–379, 2019.
- [38] A. Garrod and A. Ghosh, "A review of bifacial solar photovoltaic applications," *Frontiers in Energy*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 704–726, 2023.
- [39] O. Rejeb, L. Gaillard, S. Giroux-Julien, C. Ghenai, A. Jemni, M. Bettayeb, and C. Menezo, "Novel solar pv/thermal collector design for the enhancement of thermal and electrical performances," *Renewable energy*, vol. 146, pp. 610–627, 2020.
- [40] S. Adhya, D. Saha, A. Das, J. Jana, and H. Saha, "An iot based smart solar photovoltaic remote monitoring and control unit," in *2016 2nd international conference on control, instrumentation, energy & communication (CIEC)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 432–436.
- [41] Z. N. Ndalloka, H. V. Nair, S. Alpert, and C. Schmid, "Solar photovoltaic recycling strategies," *Solar Energy*, vol. 270, p. 112379, 2024.
- [42] K. Moradi, F. Jafari, F. Moghaddam, and Q. Shafiee, "Modeling of photovoltaic-thermal systems using multivariate polynomial regression," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 136–143, 2024.
- [43] H. Zhou, Y. Zhang, L. Yang, Q. Liu, K. Yan, and Y. Du, "Short-term photovoltaic power forecasting based on long short term memory neural network and attention mechanism," *Ieee Access*, vol. 7, pp. 78 063–78 074, 2019.
- [44] A. H. Al-Waeli, K. Sopian, J. H. Yousif, H. A. Kazem, J. Boland, and M. T. Chaichan, "Artificial neural network modeling and analysis of photovoltaic/thermal system based on the experimental study," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 186, pp. 368–379, 2019.